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Notes on ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) of Lesbos island, Greece

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Abstract: With an area of 1,633 km² and approximately 400 km of coastline, Lesbos is the third-largest Greek island and the eighth-largest in the Mediterranean. Situated in the northeastern part of the Aegean archipelago and bordering Turkey, Lesbos has been known to host 59 ant species and morphospecies. In this article, we present a list of 84 ant species and morphospecies collected in Lesbos. The checklist is a compilation of a literature data and material surveys of the materials collected in 2015, 2022, and 2024. Seven species are new to the East Aegean Islands, and 25 are recorded from Lesbos for the first time. *Strongylognathus afer* EMERY, 1884, is a new species for the fauna of Greece.

Key words: ants, faunistics, Greece, Lesbos, north-eastern Aegean, taxonomy.

INTRODUCTION

Greece is considered a biodiversity hotspot (MYERS *et al.* 2000) and a rarity centre for ants (KASS *et al.* 2022). Its ant biodiversity holds more than 300 species, including numerous endemic, rare, and undescribed taxa. With more than 6,000 islands and islets in the Greek territory, its insularity and endemism levels are high, with the Aegean archipelago known to host more than three-quarters of all species known from Greece, and approximately 16% of all endemics (SCUPOLA & BOROWIEC 2023). This paper is a continuation of a series of papers focusing on the faunistic investigation of various Greek regions. So far, the project

has covered Greek islands: Cephalonia (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2014), Corfu (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2021a), Crete (SALATA *et al.* 2020), the Dodecanese (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2021), Euboea (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018d), Lemnos (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2022), Samos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018b), Samothraki (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2022), Thasos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2022a, b, BOROWIEC *et al.* 2022), Zakynthos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018c), as well as parts of mainland provinces: Epirus (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018a), Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017a, 2021b, 2024), Thessaly (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018e, BOROWIEC *et al.* 2024), and Thrace (BRAČKO *et al.* 2016). Numerous new faunistic data were also provided in several faunistic and taxonomic papers (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012, 2013, CsÖSZ *et al.* 2018, SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015, 2017, 2018, 2019a, 2019b, 2019c, 2022, BOROWIEC *et al.* 2023a, 2023b, SALATA *et al.* 2018a, 2018b, 2019, 2021, 2023a, 2023b, 2024, SCUPOLA & BOROWIEC 2023, DEMETRIOU *et al.* 2023, ZIĘCINA *et al.* 2024).

With an area of 1,633 km² and approximately 400 kilometers of coastline, Lesvos (in Greek: Λέσβος, romanized: Lésvos or Lesbos) is the third largest Greek island and the eighth largest in the Mediterranean Sea. It is located in the northeastern Aegean Sea and belongs to the North Aegean Islands administrative region, forming a separate regional unit with its capital Mytilini. The eastern coast faces the Turkish coast and at the narrowest point, the Mytilene Strait, is about 5.5 km wide. The total population was 83,755 in 2021 and a third of them live in the capital, while the remainder are spread in small towns and villages. Nevertheless, large areas of the arid western part of the island are practically uninhabited. The island is under moderate tourist pressure, with most tourist resorts located on its north-eastern coast. The island has a hot-summer Mediterranean climate. The mean annual temperature is 18°C, and the mean annual rainfall is 750 mm. Its exceptional sunshine makes it one of the sunniest islands in the Aegean Sea. Snow and very low temperatures are rare. In recent years, temperatures have been reaching 40°C from June to September (Climatic Atlas of Greece, <http://climatlas.hnms.gr/sdi/> 2024).

Two separate environmental zones can be distinguished on the island, the eastern and central-eastern regions are largely forested or with Mediterranean shrublands (Figs 2–7), while the western part is largely deforested and covered with maquis-type vegetation (phrygana, Figs 8, 9). The eastern part of the island is dominated by pine forests (Figs 2, 3), while the mountainous areas and central part of the island are dominated by oak forests (Fig. 5). In the central part of the southern coast there are large saltpans, surrounded by meadows with saline soil (Figs 10, 11). Around the tourist resorts and villages there are dry hills with xerothermophilous vegetation and shrubs (Fig. 4). Generally, forests occupy 20% of the island, and in the remaining part of the forested area predominate scrub. Although the landscape is generally mountainous, the two highest peaks do not exceed 1000 m (Mt. Lepetymnos reaches up to 968 m and Mt. Olympus up to 967 m). The olive groves cover about 400 km², that is 1/4, of the island, with nearly 11 million olive trees accounting for approximately 20% of the Greek olive oil production. The largest part of the olive groves is cultivated in a sustainable and organic manner, with minimal (if any) human intervention in cultivation efforts and means (Public Entity for Culture, Tourism & Sports of the Municipality of West Lesvos, <https://welcometolesvos.com/> 2024).

According to the latest published catalogue of ants on Aegean islands, Lesvos hosts 59 species and morphospecies of ants (SCUPOLA & BOROWIEC 2023). In this study, three collecting trips to Lesvos raise the overall ant biodiversity of the island to a total of 84 species, including 25 newly recorded for Lesvos as well as the first record of *Strongylognathus afer* EMERY, 1884 from Greece.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A total of 105 collecting sites were sampled, covering virtually all terrestrial habitats on the island (Fig. 1), during the course of three collecting trips in 2015, 2022, and 2024. Between the 5th – 12th of June 2015, material was collected by L. Borowiec, during the period of 12th – 16th of October 2022 by J. Demetriou, C. Georgiadis, and J.K Wetterer, and during the 5th – 18th of June 2024 by L. Borowiec and D. Zięcina. Species collected in 2015 were partially mentioned in some taxonomic papers which are noted for each species, and almost all species collected in 2015 were reported for the first time in SCUPOLA & BOROWIEC (2023) without detailed locality data.

The main method, applied at all sites, was direct sampling (hand collecting) and Davis sifters. Ant nests and individual specimens were collected on the ground, in leaf litter, under stones, in dead wood, on tree trunks and twigs. Ants were brushed off to an entomological umbrella on the roadsides and forest. Nests were also searched in rock cracks and on cracked stones using a chisel. All specimens were preserved in 75% or 96% ethanol.

Distribution in Greece refers to BOROWIEC (2014), SALATA & BOROWIEC (2018), and unpublished data from the Database and Collection of Greek Ants (DCGA), preserved at the University of Wrocław. When assigning distribution records to the Greek regions, we decided not to follow the country's new administrative division implemented on January 1, 2011. That is due to the fact that in the very first catalog of Greek ants (LEGAKIS 2011) distributional data were based on the old regional division, and some records had been assigned only to the province level without exact locality data. As such, it is difficult to assign them to a specific new regional unit. Geographical coordinates are given in decimal degrees. For the parasitic species of the *Temnothorax* complex, generic names previously proposed for paraphyletic lineages were used (*Chalepoxenus* and *Myrmoxenus*). Materials are deposited in the Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław (in temporary deposit by Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy, Myrmecological Lab - DBET), and the Zoology Museum of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (ZMUA).

LIST OF LOCALITIES

The site number refers to the Locality Code used in the Database of Greek Ants stored at Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy.

5-12 June 2015 leg. L. Borowiec

LES-238 – Anaxos Skoutarou, 4 m, 6-7 VI 2015, 39.31839 / 26.14776, urban area.

LES-239 – Anaxos Skoutarou, 28 m, 7 VI 2015, 39.31701 / 26.14061, dry hill.

LES-240 – near Anemotia, 352 m, 8 VI 2015, 39.24127 / 26.10958, pastures with small oaks.

LES-241 – near Antissa, 74 m, 8 VI 2015, 39.23841 / 25.99782, mediterranean oak forest with rocks and stones.

LES-242 – Moni Pithariou, 99 m, 8 VI 2015, 39.17322 / 25.96195, stream valley with plane trees.

LES-243 – 3.4 km NE of Skalochori, 292 m, 9 VI 2015, 39.27923 / 26.10926, mediterranean oak forest with rocks and stones.

LES-244 – 3 km N of Kalloni, 191 m, 9 VI 2015, 39.26158 / 26.2073, pine forest.

LES-245 – Kalloni salines, 3 m, 10 VI 2015, 39.21687 / 26.26662, salt pans.

LES-246 – near Ahladeri, 9 m, 10 VI 2015, 39.15958 / 26.29292, pine forest with rocks and stones.

- LES-247 – Piges Pesa, 113 m, 10 VI 2015, 39.12736 / 26.26342, stream valley in pine forest.
 LES-248 – 1.7 km NW of Megali Limni, 381 m, 10 VI 2015, 39.11343 / 26.30738, pine forest.
 LES-249 – Mt. Olympos, 814 m, 10 VI 2015, 39.06958 / 26.34976, pine forest with shrubs.
 LES-250 – Ligona Valley, 229 m, 11 VI 2015, 39.32734 / 26.21009, stream valley with plane trees.
 LES-251 – Ipsilometopo, 485 m, 11 VI 2015, 39.32012 / 26.24461, oak forest.
 LES-252 – Argennos, 548 m, 12 VI 2015, 39.35494 / 26.2661, oak forest.
 LES-253 – Sykaminia, 305 m, 12 VI 2015, 39.3586 / 26.2911, oak forest.
 LES-254 – rd. Sykaminia-Vigla, 395 m, 12 VI 2015, 39.35468 / 26.30483, oak forest.

12-16 October 2022, leg. J. Demetriou, C. Georgiadis, J.K. Wetterer

- LES-280 – Afalonas, 80 m, 12 X 2022, 39.1468 / 26.5165, roadside.
 LES-280a – Afalonas, 80 m, 12 X 2022, 39.1466 / 26.5166, next to the parking lot, *Platanus*, water.
 LES-281 – Mitilini, marina, 1 m, 12 X 2022, 39.0964 / 26.5572, urban area.
 LES-281a – Marina Yacht Club, 2 m, 12 X 2022, 39.0967 / 26.5569, parking lot, urban landscaping, pavement.
 LES-282, 283 – Agia Paraskevi Karaağaç, 849 m, 12 X 2022, 39.0474 / 26.3840, mixed forest and church area.
 LES- 283a – Agia Paraskevi Karaağaç, 855 m, 12 X 2022, 39.0478 / 26.3858, mixed forest and oaks.
 ES- 283b – Agios Nektarios, 860 m, 12 X 2022, 39.0522 / 26.3821, oaks, urban landscaping.
 LES-284, 285, 285a – Mitilini, NE University Campus, 48-50 m, 12 X 2022, 39.0845 / 26.5686, urban habitat, disturbed.
 LES-286 – Mitilini, SE University Campus, 35-37 m, 13 X 2022, 39.0850 / 26.5695, urban habitat, disturbed.
 LES-287 – Moni Agios Rafail, 180 m, 13 X 2022, 39.1706 / 26.4811, monastery area.
 LES-287a – Moni Agios Rafail, 180 m, 13 X 2022, 39.1700 / 26.4816, flowerpots, urban landscaping.
 LES-288, 289, 290 – Vrachodis, 222 m, 13 X 2022, 39.3034 / 26.3372, shrubland and phrygana.
 LES-290a – Vrachodis, 220 m, 13 X 2022, 39.3030 / 26.3372, shrubland and phrygana.
 LES-291 – Moaeno, 100 m, 13 X 2022, 39.2471 / 26.2888, dirt road.
 LES-291a – Moaeno, 95 m, 13 X 2022, 39.2468 / 26.2888, next to small lake, disturbed habitat, dirt road.
 LES-292, 294, 294a – Agorotos, 165 m, 13 X 2022, 39.2553 / 26.3088, olive grove and *Platanus*, mixed forest, next to stream.
 LES-295, 296, 297, 297a – Petrovouni, 3.7 km W of Pigi, 265-267 m, 13 X 2022, 39.1854 / 26.3733, *Pinus brutia* forest.
 LES-298, 299, 300, 301, 301a – Charamida, 9 m, 14 X 2022, 39.0218 / 26.5459, olive grove, under rocks.

- LES-303 – Neroutsika, 30 m, 14 X 2022, 39.0188 / 26.5705, next to the road, burned phrygana.
- LES-303a – Mitilini, 3 m, 14 X 2022, 39.0380 / 26.6120, roadside.
- LES-304 – Fykiotrypa, 6 m, 14 X 2022, 39.1115 / 26.5666, urban, pots, urban landscaping.
- LES-305, 306, 307 – Kalloni, -1-1 m, 15 X 2022, 39.2167 / 26.2665, salt pans and next to dirt road.
- LES-308, 309, 309a – Sigri, 13 m, 15 X 2022, 39.2115 / 25.8523, urban pots, urban landscaping.
- LES-310 – Mitilini, hotel, 25 m, 16 X 2022, 39.0870 / 26.5647, urban area.
- LES-311, 312, 314, 314a – Kovelis bridge, 90-92 m, 16 X 2022, 39.1220 / 26.3762, stream valley.
- LES-316, 317, 318, 319, 320, 320a – Stavrolagada, 148 m, 16 X 2022, 39.1106 / 26.3616.
- LES-321, 322, 324, 325, 326, 327, 328, 330, 330a – Mikri Limni, 205 m, 16 X 2022, 39.1110 / 26.2652, open meadow, sparse oaks, under stones.
- LES-333 – Agios Fokas, 15 m, 16 X 2022, 39.0060 / 26.1698, disturbed dirt area.
- LES-333a – Agios Fokas, 15 m, 16 X 2022, 39.0060 / 26.1696, *Astragalus*, open phrygana, disturbed dirt area.
- 5-18 June 2024, leg. L. Borowiec & D. Zięcina**
- LES-341 – Anaxos Hill, Hotel Clara area, 34 m, 5 VI 2024, 39.3215 / 26.15913, hotel area and surroundings.
- LES-342 – rd to Petri, 112 m, 6 VI 2024, 39.32082 / 26.19454, bushes at roadsides, in umbrella.
- LES-343 – 540 m N of Petri, 134 m, 6 VI 2024, 39.32385 / 26.19639, dry hill with phrygana and small oaks.
- LES-344 – Ligona Valley loc. 1, 231 m, 6 VI 2024, 39.32731 / 26.21011, dry hill with small oaks, under stones.
- LES-345 – Ligona Valley loc. 2, 244 m, 6 VI 2024, 39.3268 / 26.2126, stream valley with plane trees.
- LES-346 – Terrapin pool ad Skalochoi, 370 m, 7 VI 2024, 39.26674 / 26.08466, luminous and dry oak forest.
- LES-347 – 1.2 km N of Skalochoi, 327 m, 7 VI 2024, 39.27069 / 26.06951, dry hill with small oaks.
- LES-348 – 1.2 km SE of Kalo Limani, 91 m, 7 VI 2024, 39.28501 / 26.05095, dry pasture with oaks.
- LES-349 – Paralia Kokkino Limani, 9 m, 7 VI 2024, 39.28566 / 26.03027, gravel beach with rocks.
- LES-349a – Ancient Antissa, 2 m, 7 VI 2024, 39.29075 / 26.01809, dirt road close to archeological ruins.
- LES-350 – Paralia Kampos, 7 m, 7 VI 2024, 39.27999 / 25.00298, shrubs and herbs at roadsides, in umbrella.
- LES-351 – Liota, 81 m, 7 VI 2024, 39.26745 / 25.965787, village area.
- LES-352 – 720 m N of Liota, 71 m, 7 VI 2024, 39.27621 / 25.96365, inside basal part of dry stems of large Apiaceae plants.

- LES-353 – near Vafios, 296 m, 8 VI 2024, 39.34530 / 26.22385, rock at roadsides.
- LES-354 – 900 m SW of Argennos, 583 m, 8 VI 2024, 39.35245 / 26.25811, on rocks and under stones close to roadside.
- LES-355 – near Argennos, 576 m, 8 VI 2024, 39.35505 / 26.26372, rocky mountain slopes with small oaks.
- LES-356 – Mt Vigla loc. 1, 700 m, 8 VI 2024, 39.34484 / 26.28108, mountain pasture with sparse oaks.
- LES-357 – Mt Vigla loc. 2, 575 m, 8 VI 2024, 39.35294 / 26.29482, dirt roadsides with sparse oaks.
- LES-358 – Antissa, 289 m, 9 VI 2024, 39.237344 / 25.97593, group of cypresses in suburban area.
- LES-359 – Ipsilou Monastery, 505 m, 9 VI 2024, 39.23174 / 25.93548, rocks at roadsides to monastery.
- LES-360 – road to Petrified Forest, 275 m, 9 VI 2024, 39.23061 / 25.90327, phrygana.
- LES-361 – 1.8 km S of Sigiri, 3 m, 9 VI 2024, 39.19743 / 25.8558, phrygana.
- LES-362 – rd to Paralia Tsichliodas, 3 m, 9 VI 2024, 39.17249 / 25.87449, field.
- LES-363 – near Mistegna, 82 m, 10 VI 2024, 39.21619 / 26.45576, olive plantation.
- LES-364 – near Nees Kydonies, 116 m, 10 VI 2024, 39.23398 / 26.44263, phrygana with shrubs.
- LES-365 – 1.1 km NW of Nees Kydonies, 162 m, 10 VI 2024, 39.22997 / 26.4298, pine forest with rocks.
- LES-366 – 2.7 km NE of Napi, 185 m, 10 VI 2024, 39.29129 / 26.30177, rocks along sides of periodic stream.
- LES-367 – Kalloni Salt pans, 0 m, 11 VI 2024, 39.2199 / 26.24231, salines.
- LES-368 – Parakoila, 85 m, 11 VI 2024, 39.17463 / 26.14073, small pine forest.
- LES-369 – rd Parakoila-Anemotia loc. 1, 125 m, 11 VI 2024, 39.1805 / 26.12708, pine forest.
- LES-370 – rd Parakoila-Anemotia loc. 2, 202 m, 11 VI 2024, 39.1866 / 26.12278, pine forest.
- LES-371 – rd Parakoila-Anemotia loc. 3, 276 m, 11 VI 2024, 39.18614 / 26.11627, pine forest.
- LES-372 – rd Parakoila-Anemotia loc. 4, 461 m, 11 VI 2024, 39.1985 / 26.1129, pine forest.
- LES-373 – rd Parakoila-Anemotia loc. 5, 452 m, 11 VI 2024, 39.24016 / 26.10027, from herbs on roadsides, in umbrella.
- LES-374 – near Ahladeri, 16 m, 12 VI 2024, 39.1473 / 26.27538, shrubs at roadsides of cypress alley, in umbrella.
- LES-375 – 1.8 km S of Ahladeri, 120 m, 12 VI 2024, 39.13737 / 26.27223, pine forest.
- LES-376 – rd to Mt Olympus peak, 685 m, 12 VI 2024, 39.07643 / 26.32858, pine forest.
- LES-377 – Mt Olympus, 725 m, 12 VI 2024, 39.07453 / 26.34655, pine forest.
- LES-378 – 2 km SW of Agiasos, 744 m, 12 VI 2024, 39.06689 / 26.35919, olive plantation.
- LES-379 – rd to Sanatorio, 653 m, 12 VI 2024, 39.066 / 26.37288, chestnut forest.
- LES-380 – near Sanatorio, 671 m, 12 VI 2024, 39.06346 / 26.3929, mixed forest.
- LES-381 – Pigi Tsingou, 200 m, 12 VI 2024, 39.10071 / 26.352251, source of drinking water.

- LES-382 – Peloti, 420 m, 13 VI 2024, 39.32361 / 26.28157, stone walls and trees around chapel.
- LES-383 – Mt Lepetimos, rd to Profitis Ilias loc. 1, 882 m, 13 VI 2024, 39.33308 / 26.24952, alpine zone with ferns and stones.
- LES-384 – Mt Lepetimos, rd to Profitis Ilias loc. 2, 802 m, 13 VI 2024, 39.33847 / 26.25249, olive and hawthorns forest with rocks.
- LES-385 – Mt Lepetimos, rd to Profitis Ilias, 746 m, 13 VI 2024, 39.33728 / 26.25499, mediterranean oak forest with stones.
- LES-386 – Mt Lepetimos, rd to Profitis Ilias loc. 4, 630 m, 13 VI 2024, 39.33042 / 26.26065, mediterranean oak forest with stones.
- LES-387 – rd Peloti-Ipsilometopo, 432 m, 13 VI 2024, 39.318752 / 26.27368, pasture with large oaks and stones.
- LES-388 – rd Ag. Paraskevi-Pigi loc. 1, 84 m, 14 VI 2024, 39.22526 / 26.3198, pine forest with rocks and stones.
- LES-389 – rd Ag. Paraskevi-Pigi loc. 2, 114 m, 14 VI 2024, 39.22366 / 26.33429, pine forest.
- LES-390 – rd Ag. Paraskevi-Pigi loc. 3, 168 m, 14 VI 2024, 39.23141 / 26.35105, pine forest.
- LES-391 – rd Ag. Paraskevi-Pigi loc. 4, 226 m, 14 VI 2024, 39.2231 / 26.3653, pine forest.
- LES-392 – 2.4 km W of Pigi, 359 m, 14 VI 2024, 39.17915 / 26.3889, dirt road in pine forest.
- LES-393 – rd to Petra, 196 m, 14 VI 2024, 39.26493 / 26.20797, pine forest.
- LES-394 – 1.6 km E of Antissa, 71 m, 15 VI 2024, 39.23801 / 25.99794, riverbed.
- LES-395 – 2.6 km SW of Antissa, 239 m, 15 VI 2024, 39.215 / 25.95996, riverbed.
- LES-396 – Moni Pithariou, 76 m, 15 VI 2024, 39.1731 / 25.96185, stream valley with plane trees.
- LES-397 – 3 km SW of Skoutaros, 311 m, 16 VI 2024, 39.27597 / 26.10595, pastures with broad leaf oaks.
- LES-398 – Pterounda, 259 m, 16 VI 2024, 39.21157 / 26.05473, cracked rock in pine forest.
- LES-399 – 700 m NW of Pterounda, 295 m, 16 VI 2024, 39.21595 / 26.04893, large stones on roadsides at pine tree.
- LES-400 – near Hidira, 189 m, 16 VI 2024, 39.20636 / 26.0344, large stones on roadsides and in stream valley.
- LES-401 – rd to Agra, 358 m, 16 VI 2024, 39.18393 / 26.0401, rocks at roadsides.
- LES-402 – 3.8 km N of Kalloni, 229 m, 17 VI 2024, 39.26708 / 26.21031, pine forest.
- LES-403 – rd to Klapados, 310 m, 17 VI 2024, 39.27316 / 26.20473, pine forest with small oaks.
- LES-404 – near Klapados waterfall, 372 m, 17 VI 2024, 39.27411 / 26.19514, pine forest with sparse oaks.
- LES-405 – Klapados, 385 m, 17 VI 2024, 39.28489 / 26.19593, plane forest with rocks and stones.
- LES-405A – Petra city, 8 m, 18 VI 2024, 39.3264 / 26.17505, urban area.

Fig. 1. Map of location of collecting sites.

LIST OF SPECIES

(species recorded from Lesvos for the first time marked with an asterisk)

1. *Aphaenogaster aktaci* KIRAN & TEZCAN, 2008

Localities: 249, 250, 252, 285, 286, 287, 345, 356, 384, 385.

Note: Material from localities 249, 250, 252 was first noted by SALATA & BOROWIEC (2018). In Greece, this species is known only from Lesvos.

2. *Aphaenogaster balcanica* (EMERY, 1898)

Localities: 250, 251, 285a, 286, 301a, 304, 342, 343, 344, 345, 354, 367, 383, 384, 385, 405A.

Note: It is a common species, recorded from all mainland provinces, Cyclades, the Ionian Islands, and the East Aegean Islands. The single record from the Dodecanese probably refers to populations established from introduced individuals.

3. *Aphaenogaster epirotes* (EMERY, 1895)

Localities: 243, 250, 251, 252, 254, 344, 357, 404.

Note: Material from localities 243, 250, 251, 252, and 254 was first noted from Lesvos by ZIĘCINA *et al.* (2024). It is known from all mainland provinces, Cyclades, the East Aegean Islands, and the Ionian Islands.

4. *Aphaenogaster festae* EMERY, 1915

Localities: 241, 242, 243, 251, 254, 318, 319, 341, 358, 400.

Note: Material from localities 241, 242, 243, 251, and 254 was first noted by SALATA & BOROWIEC (2021). It is an eastern species recorded only from the East Aegean Islands, Dodecanese, and Thrace, with a single record from Thasos island of Macedonia.

5. *Aphaenogaster splendida* (ROGER, 1859)*

Locality: 351.

Note: It is a rare species in Greece, known only from single records from Crete, Kos, and Samos, all sites are limited to anthropogenic areas. In Lesvos, it was found in a mountain village in a darkened cellar doorway.

6. *Aphaenogaster subterranea* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 250, 384, 385.

Note: Recorded first from Lesvos as *Aphaenogaster pallida* v. *lesbica* n. v. by FOREL (1913) and in further papers this form was treated as separate species, but the most recent revision of the *A. subterranea* species group (ZIĘCINA *et al.* 2024) showed its conspecificity with *Aphaenogaster subterranea* (LATREILLE). Material from locality 250 was noted from Lesvos by ZIĘCINA *et al.* (2024). It is a very common species so far noted from all Greek provinces except Crete.

7. *Camponotus aegaeus* EMERY, 1915

Localities: 243, 247, 248, 250, 330, 341, 342, 343, 344, 346, 358, 368, 370, 377, 382, 387, 388, 389, 390, 392, 398.

Note: It is an eastern species, recorded from the East Aegean Islands, the Dodecanese, eastern Macedonia, and Thrace.

8. *Camponotus aethiops* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 238, 240, 243, 244, 254, 297a, 328, 346, 348, 361, 362, 372, 376, 384, 404, 405A.

Note: It is a common species, recorded from all Greek provinces.

9. *Camponotus boghossiani* FOREL, 1911

Localities: 250, 251, 254, 343, 355, 357, 363, 370, 380, 404, 405.

Note: Material from localities 250, 251, and 254 was first noted by SALATA & BOROWIEC (2018). It is a southern and eastern species recorded from Crete, Cyclades, the Dodecanese, and the East Aegean Islands. In the Greek mainland, it is rare, known only from the Peloponnese.

10. *Camponotus dalmaticus* (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 246, 361, 373, 374.

Note: It is a northern and western species in Greece, known from all mainland provinces, the Aegean Islands, and Ionian Islands.

11. *Camponotus fallax* (NYLANDER, 1856)

Localities: 254, 282, 355.

Note: It is an uncommon species in mainland Greece and a rare species on the islands recorded from the East Aegean Islands, the Ionian Islands, and the Dodecanese.

12. *Camponotus gestroi* EMERY, 1878

Localities: 239, 240, 250, 343, 344, 346, 348, 363, 397.

Note: It is an uncommon species recorded from all provinces except Epirus.

13. *Camponotus ionius* EMERY, 1920

Localities: 247, 294, 294a, 299, 301a, 303, 309a, 311, 314a, 363, 389, 390, 391.

Note: It is a common species known from all Greek provinces except Crete.

14. *Camponotus kiesenwetteri* (ROGER, 1859)

Localities: 239, 240, 251, 254, 292, 294a, 300, 301a, 303, 333, 342, 343, 344, 346, 350, 365, 369, 370, 372, 375, 393, 397, 398, 400, 402, 404.

Note: From Lesbos first recorded by FINZI (1939). It is a common species associated with pine forests and trees, so far not recorded only from Epirus and Thessaly.

15. *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER, 1792)

Localities: 238, 239, 240, 241, 242, 244, 246, 249, 250, 251, 252, 253, 254, 283a, 286, 290a, 297, 297a, 300, 301a, 303A, 312, 314a, 316, 320a, 322, 333, 341, 342, 343, 344, 345, 346, 347, 348, 350, 351, 353, 354, 355, 356, 357, 358, 359, 365, 366, 370, 371, 372, 373, 374, 375, 376, 377, 378, 380, 381, 382, 383, 384, 386, 388, 389, 390, 393, 396, 397, 399, 400, 401, 402, 403, 404, 405, 405A.

Note: It is one of the commonest Greek species of *Camponotus* recorded from all regions.

16. *Camponotus oertzeni* FOREL, 1889

Localities: 243, 249, 346, 357, 377, 383, 384, 386.

Note: Material from localities 243 and 249 was first noted by SALATA & BOROWIEC (2018). It is a common Greek species often misidentified with *Camponotus aethiops*, known from all provinces except Cyclades.

17. *Camponotus piceus* (LEACH, 1825)

Locality: 254.

Note: It is a common species in mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands, rare in Crete and the East Aegean Islands.

18. *Camponotus samius* FOREL, 1889

Localities: 239, 240, 247, 250, 251, 254, 285, 285a, 299, 301a, 314, 344, 346, 357, 358, 363, 364, 397, 398, 402, 403, 404.

Note: It is an eastern and southern species recorded from Cyclades, the Dodecanese, the East Aegean Islands, eastern Macedonia, Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, and Thrace.

19. *Camponotus sanctus* FOREL, 1904

Localities: 238, 239, 240, 243, 244, 246, 249, 250, 251, 254, 290, 291, 291a, 303, 330a, 341, 352, 359, 360, 377, 382, 393, 395.

Note: It is an eastern species recorded only from the East Aegean Islands, and the Dodecanese.

20. *Cardiocondyla mauritanica* FOREL, 1890

Localities: 304, 309a.

Note: It is a tramp species known from urban areas and tourist resorts. Recorded from Crete, Cyclades, the Dodecanese, the Aegean Islands, the Ionian Islands, and in mainland only from Peloponnese and Sterea Ellas (Attica).

21. *Cataglyphis nodus* (BRULLÉ, 1833)*

Localities: 238, 239, 240, 241, 242, 245, 247, 250, 251, 252, 254, 290, 290a, 291, 291a, 294, 294a, 299, 301a, 308, 309a, 330a, 341, 343, 344, 346, 348, 349, 349a, 350, 351, 355,

356, 359, 360, 362, 363, 364, 365, 367, 369, 370, 372, 376, 378, 379, 382, 383, 384, 388, 389, 392, 394, 395, 398, 401, 402, 403, 405A.

Note: It is a common species recorded from most of the regions, except Cyclades, and with one doubtful record from Crete.

22. *Cataglyphis viaticoides* (ANDRÉ, 1881)

Localities: 239, 250, 251, 252, 254, 392.

Note: First recorded from Lesvos by BOROWIEC *et al.* (2021) without detailed locality data. It is a rare species recorded only from the East Aegean Islands and Thrace

23. *Chalepoxenus curtisetosus* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2015*

Localities: 348, 383, 397.

Note: It is a social parasite in nests of various species of the genus *Temnothorax*, especially of the *T. recedens* group. In Lesvos, collected in nests of *Temnothorax antigoni* (FOREL) and *T. kemali* (SANTSCHI). In Greece it is a very rare species recorded only from Samos island of the East Aegean Islands.

24. *Colobopsis truncata* (SPINOLA, 1808)

Localities: 250, 344, 389, 403.

Note: It is a moderately common species recorded from all regions.

25. *Crematogaster ionia* FOREL, 1911

Localities: 238, 240, 241, 242, 244, 246, 247, 248, 250, 251, 253, 254, 283a, 283b, 284, 285a, 286, 288, 292, 294a, 295, 297a, 300, 301a, 308, 309a, 311, 314a, 320, 330a, 333, 341, 342, 343, 344, 345, 346, 347, 348, 350, 351, 354, 355, 356, 357, 361, 363, 364, 365, 366, 368, 369, 370, 371, 372, 373, 374, 375, 376, 377, 380, 381, 382, 384, 386, 387, 388, 389, 390, 393, 394, 395, 396, 397, 398, 399, 400, 401, 402, 403, 404, 405A.

Note: First recorded from Lesvos by FOREL (1913) under the name *Crematogaster scutellaris* OL. v. *ionia* FOR. It is a very common arboricole species recorded from all Greek regions but with doubtful records from Epirus. Our unpublished molecular data suggest that this taxon is probably a complex of three cryptic species.

26. *Crematogaster lorteti* FOREL, 1910

Locality: 251.

Note: In Greece, it is a very rare species, known only from the East Aegean Islands, Macedonia, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly, and Thrace.

27. *Crematogaster schmidtii* (MAYR, 1853)

Localities: 239, 254, 330a, 358, 405.

Note: It is a common species in the north and central mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands, rare in the southern mainland, and the East Aegean Islands, a single record from Crete in urban area is probably based on an introduced colony.

28. *Crematogaster sordidula* (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 240, 243, 254, 354, 355, 360, 363, 389, 397.

Note: First recorded from Lesvos by FOREL (1913). It is a common species recorded from all Greek regions.

29. *Dolichoderus quadripunctatus* (LINNAEUS, 1771)

Localities: 241, 250, 342, 345, 351, 405A.

Note: It is a moderately common species recorded from most regions, except Crete and Cyclades.

30. *Formica clara* FOREL, 1886
 Localities: 238, 239.
 Note: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland, in islands known only from Lesvos.
31. *Hypoponera eduardi* (FOREL, 1894)*
 Locality: 304.
 Note: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland, known from the Aegean Islands, Crete, Dodecanese, Epirus, the Ionian islands, Macedonia, and Peloponnese. Most records are from anthropogenic sites, close to streams, rivers, and ponds.
32. *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER, 1850)
 Localities: 243, 247, 249, 250, 251, 252, 254.
 Note: It is a common species recorded from all regions.
33. *Lasius illyricus* ZIMMERMANN, 1935
 Locality: 250.
 Note: It is a common species in the Greek mainland and rare in Crete. In the Aegean Islands area known only from Lesvos.
34. *Lasius lasioides* (EMERY, 1869)*
 Localities: 282, 285, 308, 311, 327.
 Note: It is a common species recorded from all regions.
35. *Lasius neglectus* VAN LOON, BOOMSMA & ANDRASALVY, 1990
 Localities: 238, 246, 253, 287a, 314a, 320a, 342, 345, 354, 357, 363, 405A.
 Note: The status of the *Lasius* species of the *L. turcicus* complex was reclassified recently (SEIFERT 2020), and re-examination of materials from Greece showed that *L. neglectus* predominates in low altitudes while in mountains prevails *L. turcicus* SANTSCHI. The third species, *Lasius precursor* SEIFERT was described from the Aegean area. So far, only *L. turcicus* has not been recorded from Lesvos.
36. *Lasius precursor* SEIFERT, 2020*
 Localities: 283a, 370, 381, 400.
 Note: It is a recently described species known only from the western Turkey and Kos island of the Dodecanese Archipelago. Records from Lesvos are the second from Greece and the first to the East Aegean Islands.
37. *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR, 1855)
 Localities: 238, 239, 240, 241, 242, 243, 244, 245, 247, 248, 250, 251, 252, 254, 280, 280a, 281, 281a, 283b, 287a, 288, 290a, 292, 294a, 298, 301a, 303, 304, 305, 307, 309a, 314a, 325, 341, 342, 343, 346, 349, 350, 351, 354, 355, 357, 358, 360, 363, 367, 368, 369, 370, 371, 372, 373, 377, 381, 382, 383, 384, 387, 389, 390, 392, 396, 398, 400, 405A.
 Note: The status of the Aegean populations of the *Lepisiota* species from the *frauenfeldi* complex is still uncertain. The Balkan taxa of this genus require a thorough revision based on morphological characters and genetic analyses. It is a common species in Greek mainland and the Ionian Islands, rare in the Aegean Islands. Samples from Lesvos belong to the morphotype 1 with gynes mostly brown with mesosoma usually partly red and legs mostly yellow.

38. *Lepisiota* cf. *frauenfeldi* _AEGEAN

Locality: 330a.

Note: This morphotype is characterized by gynes almost completely black, including legs. It was recorded from the East Aegean Islands and Dodecaese.

39. *Liometopum microcephalum* (PANZER, 1798)

Localities: 242, 348, 351, 355, 386, 387, 396.

Note: It is a moderately common species known from all mainland provinces and the Aegean and Ionian Islands.

40. *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987

Localities: 238, 252, 291, 291a, 304, 307, 309, 309a, 354, 359, 360, 367.

Note: It is a common species recorded from all regions.

41. *Messor ibericus* SANTSCHI, 1931*

Localities: 341, 351, 357, 405A.

Note: *Messor ibericus* for many years was treated as a synonym of *M. structor*, but the recent revision of this complex showed that it is a distinct species (STEINER *et al.* 2018). Our data (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2019b) show that *M. ibericus* is the dominant species in lowland Greece and on the islands (although it has not yet been recorded from the Cyclades), while in the mountains predominates *M. structor*.

42. *Messor mcarthuri* STEINER *et al.*, 2018

Localities: 238, 239, 241, 243, 249, 250, 251, 252, 254, 280a, 307, 320a, 367.

Note: Material from localities 238, 239, 241, 243, 249, 250, 251, 252, 254 was first noted by SALATA & BOROWIEC (2019b). It is an eastern and southern species recorded from most provinces except Epirus and the Ionian Islands.

43. *Messor oertzeni* FOREL, 1910

Localities: 240, 243, 250, 251, 289, 290a, 301a, 306, 307, 330a, 347, 363, 383, 384.

Note: It is a rare eastern species recorded from the East Aegean Islands, north-eastern Macedonia, and Thrace.

44. *Messor wasmanni* KRAUSSE, 1910

Localities: 238, 240, 241, 243, 244, 245, 254, 280a, 281, 281a, 286, 290a, 292, 294a, 301a, 304, 306, 309, 330a, 333a, 345, 346, 347, 353, 354, 358, 359, 360, 363, 382, 383, 405A.

Note: It is one of the commonest Greek member of the genus *Messor* recorded from all regions.

45. *Monomorium monomorium* BOLTON, 1987

Localities: 239, 240, 246, 248, 250, 251, 254, 281, 281a, 290a, 294a, 303, 304, 308, 309a, 311, 320a, 333, 341, 351, 352, 357, 370, 377.

Note: It is a rare Mediterranean species previously treated as a tramp but probably native in Greece. Recorded from Crete, the East Aegean Islands, Epirus, the Ionian Islands, and Peloponnese.

46. *Myrmoxenus gordiagini* RUZSKY, 1902*

Locality: 380.

Note: It is a social parasite in nests of various species of the genus *Temnothorax*, in Greece,

observed in nests of *Temnothorax lichtensteini* (BONDROIT), *Temnothorax* cf. *unifasciatus* and *Temnothorax* cf. *tubерum*. In Lesvos collected in three nests of *Temnothorax angustifrons* CSŐSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ. In Greece known from Macedonia, Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, and Thessaly. New to the East Aegean Islands.

47. *Myrmoxenus kraussei* (EMERY, 1915)*

Locality: 389.

Note: It is a social parasite, in Greece observed in nests of *Temnothorax recedens* (NYLANDER). In Lesvos collected in a nest of *Temnothorax antigoni* (FOREL, 1911) belonging to the *T. recedens* species group. In Greece known from Crete, Macedonia, and Thessaly. New to the East Aegean Islands.

48. *Nylanderia jaegerskioeldi* (MAYR, 1904)*

Locality: 309a.

Note: It is a tramp species associated mostly with anthropogenic habitats. In Greece, recorded from the East Aegean Islands, Crete, Dodecanese, the Ionian Islands, Peloponnese, and Sterea Ellas. Usually collected in tourist resorts and urban areas.

49. *Pheidole indica* MAYR, 1879*

Localities: 308, 309a.

Note: It is a tramp species associated mostly with anthropogenic habitats. In Greece recorded from the East Aegean Islands, Crete, Cyclades, Dodecanese, the Ionian Islands, and Peloponnese, usually collected in tourist resorts and urban areas.

50. *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula*

Localities: 238, 239, 240, 241, 242, 243, 246, 247, 250, 251, 253, 254, 280, 280a, 283, 283b, 285, 285a, 286, 287, 291, 291a, 292, 294a, 300, 301, 301a, 304, 305, 307, 311, 314a, 320, 320a, 326, 330a, 333, 333a, 341, 342, 343, 344, 345, 347, 348, 349, 351, 352, 353, 354, 355, 356, 357, 358, 359, 363, 365, 368, 370, 371, 378, 381, 382, 384, 387, 389, 390, 394, 395, 396, 398, 400, 402, 404, 405, 405A.

Note: From Lesvos it was first recorded by FINZI (1939) under the name *Pheidole pallidula arenarum* var. *orientalis* EMERY. The Mediterranean populations of the taxon named *Pheidole pallidula* (NYLANDER, 1849) have recently been divided into four species, three of them recorded in Greece (SEIFERT 2016), but this point of view is still under discussion owing to the great local variability of this very common Mediterranean ant. Material examined by B. Seifert from Lesvos was classified under a name *Pheidole koshewnikovi* RUZSKY, 1905. This complex of taxa belongs to one of the commonest ants in Greece, recorded from all provinces.

51. *Plagiolepis pallescens* FOREL, 1889

Localities: 240, 243, 244, 247, 248, 251, 252, 253, 254, 280, 289, 294a, 333, 303, 304, 314a, 341, 342, 343, 350, 351, 354, 358, 363, 364, 365, 368, 370, 371, 372, 374, 382, 387, 389, 395, 398, 404.

Note: The status of Greek populations of the genus *Plagiolepis* is under study. According to KIRSCHNER *et al.* (2024), in Europe occur three species of the *Plagiolepis taurica* complex, two of them, *P. taurica* SANTSCHE, 1920 and *P. pallescens* FOREL, 1889, were collected in Greece. *Plagiolepis pallescens* is an eastern species known only from the East Aegean Islands and Dodecanese.

52. *Plagiolepis peperamus* SALATA, BOROWIEC & RADCHENKO, 2018

Localities: 238, 239, 245, 246, 248, 250, 281, 281a, 285, 285a, 286, 290a, 291, 291a, 295, 297a, 300, 301a, 303A, 305, 307, 308, 309a, 321, 341, 342, 350, 351, 361, 362, 364, 367, 373, 384, 393, 398, 405A.

Note: It is an uncommon species but known from all Greek provinces.

53. *Prenolepis nitens* (MAYR, 1853)

Localities: 240, 243, 248, 249, 250, 251, 252, 254, 283b.

Note: First recorded from Lesvos by FOREL (1913). It is a local forest species known from most Greek regions, except Crete, Cyclades, and Dodecanese

54. *Proformica korbi* (EMERY, 1909)*

Localities: 382, 383.

Note: It is a very rare species, recently recorded from Greece for the first time (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2023b) based on a series of specimens collected in Thrace. New to the East Aegean Islands.

55. *Solenopsis juliae* (ARAKELIAN, 1991)

Localities: 243, 254, 283b, 287a, 297, 308, 309a, 317, 324, 346, 376, 404.

Note: The status of this species was recently clarified (Csösz *et al.* 2023). In Greece it is one of the commonest members of the genus *Solenopsis*, known from all provinces except Crete. In our earlier faunistic papers from Greece and in SCUPOLA & BOROWIEC (2023) it was noted from Lesvos under the name *Solenopsis* cf. *lusitanica*.

56. *Stigmatomma denticulatum* ROGER, 1859

Locality: Recorded only generally from Lesvos by Forel (1913).

Note: It is a rare species known from the East Aegean Islands, Crete, Dodecanese, Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Peloponnese, and Thrace.

57. *Strongylognathus afer* EMERY, 1884*

Locality: 360.

Note: It is a social parasite, known from nests of *Tetramorium hungaricum* RÖSZLER and *T. semilaeve* ANDRÉ. In Lesvos, a series of workers was collected from a nest of *Tetramorium kephalosi* SALATA & BOROWIEC. Species new to the Greek fauna.

58. *Tapinoma festae* EMERY, 1925

Localities: 241, 245, 280, 285a, 286, 310, 381, 394, 396.

Note: It is an uncommon species known only from all island provinces, absent in mainland Greece.

59. *Tapinoma glabrella* (NYLANDER, 1849)*

Localities: 355, 356, 384.

Note: It is a very common species known from all provinces. Its species status was clarified recently (SEIFERT *et al.* 2024). In our earlier faunistic papers from Greece, it was noted under the name *Tapinoma* cf. *erraticum*_BALC.

60. *Temnothorax aeolius* (FOREL, 1911)*

Localities: 350, 352.

Note: It is a very rare species recorded only from the East Aegean Islands, Dodecanese, north-eastern Macedonia, and Thrace.

61. *Temnothorax* cf. *aeolius**

Locality: 375.

Note: It is an undescribed species of the *T. graecus* group. This group was revised recently (SALATA *et al.* 2023a), and the sample from locality 375 appears not to be conspecific with any members of this group. In shape of petiole is similar to the members of the *T. aeolius* complex but in colour and sculpture is more similar to *T. phaetoni* SALATA, ŚRODOŃ & BOROWIEC described from Cyclades.

62. *Temnothorax angustifrons* CSŐSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ, 2015

Localities: 240, 241, 242, 243, 249, 250, 252, 253, 254, 283b, 341, 345, 346, 355, 356, 370, 372, 376, 377, 378, 379, 380, 384, 385, 386, 397, 400, 403, 404, 405.

Note: Material from localities 240, 241, 242, 243, 249, 250, 252, 253, 254 was first noted by SALATA & BOROWIEC (2018). It is a recently described species recorded only from the East Aegean Islands and single localities in Sterea Ellas and Thrace.

63. *Temnothorax antigoni* (FOREL, 1911)

Localities: 241, 242, 244, 250, 251, 341, 343, 345, 346, 348, 355, 358, 369, 370, 387, 388, 389, 390, 393, 396, 397, 399, 400, 401, 403, 404, 405.

Note: Material from localities 241, 242, 244, 250, and 251 was first recorded from Lesvos by SALATA & BOROWIEC (2015). It is an eastern species known only from the East Aegean Islands, Dodecanese, and Thrace.

64. *Temnothorax bulgaricus* (FOREL, 1892)

Localities: 240, 241, 242, 244, 246, 250, 251, 253, 254, 311, 314a, 320, 320a, 341, 342, 343, 344, 345, 346, 348, 355, 357, 358, 365, 366, 369, 377, 378, 390, 398, 399, 400, 401.

Note: It is a common species known from most provinces except Crete and Cyclades.

65. *Temnothorax clypeatus* (MAYR, 1853)*

Locality: 254.

Note: It is a very rare species recorded only from the Ionian Islands and Thessaly, new to the East Aegean Islands.

66. *Temnothorax dessyi* (MENOZZI, 1936)*

Localities: 348, 370.

Note: It is a rare species recorded only from Dodecanese and Peloponnese. New to the East Aegean Islands.

67. *Temnothorax exilis* (EMERY, 1869)

Localities: 240, 241, 244, 250.

Note: The *Temnothorax exilis* complex from Greece needs revision. At least 7 morphospecies of unclear taxonomic status were collected in this country. Specimens from Lesvos belong to the morphospecies with partly fine and shiny microsculpture on the head and pronotum and with tendency to pale, yellowish to yellowish brown mesosoma. This morphotype was described under a name *Temnothorax exilis* v. *darii* (FOREL, 1911) from Izmir in the Aegean Turkey, a place located only 95 km SE from Lesvos. This form was collected also in Samos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018b).

68. *Temnothorax flavicornis* (EMERY, 1870)*

Locality: 404.

Note: It is a rare species recorded from the East Aegean Islands, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, Peloponnese, and Thessaly.

69. *Temnothorax kemali* (SANTSCHI, 1934)
Localities: 240, 243, 249, 251, 346, 353, 354, 356, 357, 383, 384, 391, 397, 404.
Note: Material from localities 240, 243, 249, and 251 was first noted by SALATA & BOROWIEC (2018). It is an eastern species known only from the East Aegean Islands, Dodecanese, and Thrace.
70. *Temnothorax mytilenes* SALATA, ŚRODOŃ & BOROWIEC, 2023
Localities: 246, 251, 342, 343, 365, 370, 374.
Note: Material from localities 246 and 251 was noted in the original description of *T. mytilenes* (SALATA *et al.* 2023). SCUPOLA & BOROWIEC (2023) noted it under a name *Temnothorax "ionia"*. It is an eastern species known only from the East Aegean Islands and Dodecanese.
71. *Temnothorax semiruber* (ANDRÉ, 1881)
Localities: 240, 243, 244, 250, 294a.
Note: It is a common species known from all provinces.
72. *Temnothorax smyrnensis* (FOREL, 1911)*
Localities: 251, 300, 301a, 333, 342, 346, 347, 348, 350, 374.
Note: It is an eastern species known only from the East Aegean Islands, Dodecanese, and Thrace.
73. *Temnothorax turcicus* (SANTSCHI, 1934)
Localities: 246, 346.
Note: It is an uncommon species known from all mainland provinces and the East Aegean Islands.
74. *Tetramorium diomedeam* EMERY, 1908
Localities: 240, 250, 281a, 290a, 291a, 294a, 360, 361, 367.
Note: It is an uncommon species known from most provinces except Sterea Ellas.
75. *Tetramorium ferox* RUZSKY, 1903*
Locality: 367.
Note: It is an uncommon species recorded mostly from island provinces, in mainland noted only from Macedonia and Thrace.
76. *Tetramorium flavidulum* SANTSCHI, 1910*
Localities: 240, 242, 245, 249, 250, 252, 296, 297a, 356, 357, 363, 377, 383, 384, 386, 394.
Note: It is a rare species, in Greece recorded only from Nisyros island of the Dodecanese Archipelago under a name *Tetramorium cf. flavidulum* (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2021). New to the East Aegean Islands.
77. *Tetramorium hippocratis* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987*
Localities: 304, 306, 360, 368.
Note: It is an eastern and southern species recorded from the East Aegean Islands, Crete, Dodecanese, and Thrace.
78. *Tetramorium immigrans* SANTSCHI, 1927
Locality: 238.
Note: It is a tramp species noted from most provinces except Epirus. Almost all records come from urban areas and tourist resorts, only in Crete observed also in natural habitats.

79. *Tetramorium indocile* SANTSCHI, 1927*

Localities: 245, 381, 405A.

Note: The specific status of this taxon was clarified only recently (Csösz *et al.* 2014), and its distribution in Greece is not fully explained. At the moment, we have verified samples from the East Aegean Islands, Crete, Dodecanese, Macedonia, Peloponnese, and Thessaly.

80. *Tetramorium kephalosi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2017

Localities: 240, 241, 242, 243, 245, 247, 252, 253, 254, 280a, 283, 283b, 285a, 286, 289, 291, 292, 300, 330a, 341, 344, 349, 354, 358, 359, 360, 361, 363, 365, 367, 370, 378, 384, 387.

Note: It is a very common species known from all provinces.

81. *Tetramorium* cf. *punctatum* LESVOS

Localities: 239, 240, 243, 249, 250, 251, 254, 301a, 354, 356, 360.

Note: This is a species belonging to the *Tetramorium punctatum* complex within the *T. semilaeve* species group characterized by a significant reduction of the striated sculpture on the frontal surface of the head. At least two morphospecies of this complex occur in Greece, but neither of them is conspecific with the true *T. punctatum* SANTSCHI, 1927 known from Italy. The morphospecies from Lesvos differs from the morphospecies from Crete in the significantly smaller size of the gynes. This complex is speciose in the Near East, and the species status of the Greek populations will be possible to clarify after a comprehensive revision of the entire complex.

82. *Tetramorium rhodium* EMERY, 1924

Localities: 242, 243, 246, 254, 307, 345, 354, 361, 367.

Note: Material from localities 242, 243, 246, and 254 was first noted by SALATA & BOROWIEC (2019c). It is an eastern species recorded only from the East Aegean Islands and Dodecanese.

83. *Tetramorium staerckei* KRATOCHVÍL, 1944

Localities: 245, 306.

Note: Material from locality 245 was first noted by SALATA & BOROWIEC (2019c). It is a little known species preferring salty habitats. Verified records come from the East Aegean Islands, Cyclades, and Thrace.

84. *Trichomyrmex perplexus* (RADCHENKO, 1997)*

Localities: 239, 240, 241, 243, 281a, 367.

Note: It is an uncommon species known from almost all provinces except Epirus.

DISCUSSION

The updated checklist of ants on Lesvos currently includes a total of 84 taxa, including five tramp species i.e. *Cardiocondyla mauritanica*, *Lasius neglectus*, *Nylanderia jaegerskioeldi*, *Pheidole indica*, and *Tetramorium immigrans* as well as a number of rare and/or range-restricted species in Greece, such as *Aphaenogaster aktaci*, *Lasius precursor*, *Proformica korbi*, *Strongylognathus afer*, *Temnothorax chypeatus*, *T. dessyi*, *T. flavicornis*, *T. mytilenes*, and *Tetramorium flavidulum*. According to the latest checklist of ants on Greek islands, Rhodes, an island of similar size (1401.0 km²) hosts 82 species and morphospecies of ants, including nine tramp species (DEMETRIOU *et al.* 2023, SCUPOLA & BOROWIEC 2023). As such, the myrmecofauna of Lesvos is considered to be well-studied but could still hold some undetected species, including records of non-native species. For example, *Stigmatomma denticulatum* was reported for Lesvos by FOREL (1913), eluding all three sampling efforts presented in this study. Data on subterranean and leaf litter ants with “cryptic” lifestyles are scarce, with additional samplings utilizing leaf litter sifters or hypogaecic pitfall traps could uncover further distributional data and species records for the Aegean islands.

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Figs. 2–3. Pine forests: on the road to Mt Olympus (2), along the stream on the road Ag. Paraskevi-Pigi (3). Photo 2 by J. Świętojańska, photo 3 by D. Zięcina.

Figs. 4–5. Dry hills above Anaxos Skoutarou (4), a luminous oak forest on the hills near Skalochori (5). Photos by J. Świętojańska.

Figs. 6–7. Rocky hills with bushy vegetation and plane and poplar trees: Ligona Valley (6), 720 m N of Liota (7). Photo 6 by J. Świętojańska, photo 7 by D. Zięcina.

Figs. 8–9. Phrygana: on the seacoast near Sigiri (8), along road to Petrified Forest (9). Photos by D. Zięcina.

Figs. 10–11. Kalloni Salt pans: saltwater pools surrounded by salt marshes in June 2015 (10), salt meadows in June 2024 (11). Photo 10 by J. Świętojańska, photo 11 by D. Zięcina.

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